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IMPROVING MARKETING MANAGEMENT AT THE ENTERPRISE

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Abstract: This article considers the importance of marketing principles in modern management theory, revealing the content of the analytical function, determining the main directions and indicators of marketing analysis, developing ways to improve marketing analysis in manufacturing enterprises.

Key words: Enterprise, competition, management system, goods, demand, supply, sales, efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

The economic reforms carried out in our country open the doors of wide opportunities for production enterprises. As a result of the benefits and preferences given to them, the increase of funds at the disposal of enterprises, the introduction of new forces and the increase of the welfare of the population serve. It is certainly gratifying to see such positive changes in our economy and the economic activity of the country. However, today we all know well that the market economy is an economic system that operates within the framework of the influence of a complex of competition and so-called struggles. In this system, some enterprises cooperate with each other, and similar enterprises are in constant competition. In their economic activities, they always meet the needs of the times,

The growing importance of internal marketing in an enterprise is reflected in its organizational structure. Marketing management is a set of functions of planning, organization, coordination, control, audit and promotion performed to increase the demand for goods and services and increase profits. Marketing management is seen as a means and philosophy of intensifying marketing activities, the purpose of which is not to organize and promote sales, but to manage demand for the company's goods and services in a competitive market.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that the competitiveness of the enterprise in the market is determined by the effectiveness of its market-oriented policy. Many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing principles and their practical application, including F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. .We can include famous scientists like Marshall.

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing, while the research carried out in the field of marketing in our country for many years was based on national characteristics. R. Ibragimov to them. Y. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhojaev, D. Rakhimova, SH. Ergashkhodjaeva and others can be included.

Thus, marketing management manages the functional and institutional activities of marketing at various hierarchical management levels of the socio-economic system in an integrated, i.e. closely related, manner.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The purpose of the study is to determine the methods of applying marketing principles in effective management of «Daka-Tex» LLC.

In order to achieve this goal, the following tasks were solved in the research:

- Importance of marketing principles in modern management theory;
- Revealing the content of the analytical function in marketing activities;
- Determining the main directions and indicators of marketing analysis;
- Analyzing the marketing activity of the selected enterprise;
- Development of ways to improve marketing analysis in production enterprises.

In the functional sense, marketing management is understood as the process of forming a decision, planning and managing its implementation.

In the institutional sense, marketing management is interpreted as leadership, management power, effective management of the achievement of the intended goal through the correct and coordinated distribution of functional tasks among all departments of the firm based on legal and organizational powers. .

The key factors that shape the marketing-management environment include culture, policy, and system or structure (table 1).

Now let's look at the economic situation in "Daka-Tex" LLC from the point of view of marketing management:

Table 1. Analysis of income, expenses and net profit of "Daka-Tex" LLC JK during 2020-2023.

Indicators	2020 year at the end (million soums)	2021 year at the end (million soums)	2022 year at the end (million soums)	2023 year at the end (million soums)
Net income from the sale of products (goods, work and services).	50,991.18	62,262.55	58 138.12	71 248.91
Cost of goods sold (goods, work and services).	41,963.90	59,041.81	54,648.53	63 347.52
Period expenses and taxes	3 843.72	2 063.21	2 508.81	4 202.35
Net profit (loss) for the reporting period	5 236.70 (12%)	1 626.45 (3%)	1 096.73 (2%)	3 682.63 (6%)

From the analysis of the above financial reports, it is clear that the company has recorded economic growth in recent years. However, it is clear from these tables that as the income from the sale of the product increases, the cost of the product also increases. We know from the above numbers and dynamics that this has a significant negative impact on the company's net profit. This situation confirms that it is necessary to review the methods of marketing management and to apply the methods of its development in the activity of the enterprise.

Againwe should add that the company does not use media such as advertising in its activities to work directly with consumers, exchange information. As for the assortment, the number of goods that satisfy the full demand of all genders is somewhat small. Considering the fact that the company has recently started its operations, these shortcomings are invisible and can be overcome.

Taking into account the above shortcomings, from the point of view of marketing, the enterprise will have to develop its own development strategy and, of course, marketing program, relying on the principles of marketing in relation to the B2B market and customers.

Marketingmanagement plays an important role in the success of any enterprise and this is especially important in the textile industry. We present below some of our suggestions on various ways of developing marketing management methods at Daka-Tex LLC.

These methods include market research, digital marketing, attending industry events, building a strong brand identity, developing custom products, and using analytics. Implementation of the marketing methods that we offer will help the enterprise to differentiate itself in a highly competitive market and ultimately ensure the growth of sales and profits.

Threadand the knitting industry is a competitive and fast-growing market. As companies in this industry seek to expand their position, it is important to understand the current trends and opportunities in the market. In this sense, we analyze the statistics and present strategies that companies can adopt to expand their position in the yarn and knitwear market.

Market trends. According to the latest market research, the global yarn and knitting market is expected to grow at USD 42.18 billion during 2022-2026 and is expected to grow at a CAGR of 5.77% during the forecast period¹. The growth of the market is primarily due to the increased demand for knitwear by the fashion and textile industries. Additionally, the rise of e-commerce platforms has made it easier for companies to tap into a wider customer base, leading to increased competition in the market.

The yarn and knitting market is a growing industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and various market trends and developments are constantly emerging. In order to expand the company's position in this market, it is very

1 https://www.reportlinker.com/p06359992/Global-Yarn-Market.html?utm_source=GNW

important to be aware of the latest market trends and consumer demands in Uzbekistan. In this paragraph, we present the results of our research on the current market trends of the yarn and knitting industry in Uzbekistan and the strategies that "Daka-Tex" LLC JSC can use to effectively expand its market position .

Table 2. Analysis of changes in the development of textile products in the Republic of Uzbekistan²(compared to the previous year, %).

Indicator	2020	2021	2022	2023
Change in Textile Product Development(%)	108.7	104.5	128.5	119.4

Above, we use the method of least squares to find the correlation equation based on the available data (table 2).

$$y = kx + b$$

In this correlation equation, we determine the parameters k and b and the correlation coefficient R using the following formulas:

$$k = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^2}$$

$$b = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 \sum_{i=1}^n y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i}{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^2}$$

$$R = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{\sqrt{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^2} \sqrt{n \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n y_i)^2}}$$

This to find the parameters, we make the following table:

Table 3. Time Series Data for Percentage Change in Y Variable (2019–2022) with Derived Statistical Measures.

Years	x (notional year)	Y (percent)		x ²	y ²
2019	1	108.7	108.7	1	11815.69
2020	2	104.5	209	4	10920.25
2021	3	128.5	385.5	9	16512.25
2022	4	119.4	477.6	16	14256.36
(sum)	10	461.1	1180.8	30	53504.55

From the above data and formulas, we find the following values:

$$k = \frac{4 \cdot 1180,8 - 10 \cdot 461,1}{4 \cdot 30 - 10 \cdot 10} = 5,61$$

$$b = \frac{30 \cdot 461,1 - 10 \cdot 1180,8}{4 \cdot 30 - 10 \cdot 10} = 101,25$$

$$R = \frac{4 \cdot 1180,8 - 10 \cdot 461,1}{\sqrt{4 \cdot 30 - 10^2} \sqrt{4 \cdot 53504,55 - 461,1^2}} \approx 0,6693;$$

As a result of these calculations:

$$y = 5,61x + 101,25 |$$

Function, and the correlation coefficient is . Since the given values are proportional to each other and the correlation coefficient is closer to 1 than 0, we can say that the relation between the trend of the values is closer to the correlation equation we have solved (table 3).

$$R \approx 0,67R > 0$$

² Based on the data of the website <https://www.stat.uz>

Of course, there are many factors that affect the market size changes, as well as uncontrollable factors such as Covid-19 and conflicts between some countries. But even in such a situation, we need a market forecast for the development of the enterprise. Through this correlation function, we can forecast the approximate growth rate of textile production in Uzbekistan for the coming years.

Table 4. Actual and Forecasted Changes in Textile Product Development (2019–2024).

Indicator	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023*	2024*
Conditional year (value of x in the formula)	1	2	3	4	5*	6*
Change in Textile Product Development(%)	108.7	104.5	128.5	119.4	129.3*	134.91*

*forecast of correlation function

This we can see from the forecast table that in the following years, the level of change in the volume of the textile production market shows a constant growth trend. And this is important information for the company's plans for the production and sale of products for the next years (table 4).

Being aware of market trends and consumer demands in Uzbekistan is important in expanding the company's position and position in the yarn and knitwear market. By adopting sustainable practices, offering traditional designs, having a strong online presence, and using natural and organic materials, Daka-Tex LLC can address current market trends in Uzbekistan and expand its market position. Analyzing statistical data and understanding market trends, conducting research and analysis, innovating products, collaborating with local designers and artisans also give the enterprise a competitive advantage,

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In short, the sales volume of «Daka-Tex» LLC JSC is increasing year by year, but it is known that its economic efficiency, as well as the share of net profit, has decreased. In such a situation, the application of marketing principles in enterprise management helps to increase its efficiency.

We offer the following methods of applying brand management methods in enterprise management:

1. Market research. Market research is a crucial step in developing effective marketing management techniques. Businesses can collect information about customer needs, preferences and behavior to inform their marketing strategies and product development. This may include identifying specific sectors, regions, or demographics that are most likely to purchase their products.

2. Digital marketing. Digital marketing is very necessary in today's digital age. Businesses can develop a strong online presence through a website, social media, and other digital channels to reach and connect with customers. This includes creating high-quality content such as tutorials, product guides and industry news that provide value to customers and position the business as a leader in the industry.

3. Participation in industrial events. Attending industry events such as trade shows is an effective way to showcase products, make connections and generate leads. It can also provide valuable networking opportunities and insight into the latest trends and innovations in the market.

4. Brand identity. Developing a strong brand identity is also essential to differentiate products from competitors and resonate with target audiences. Creating a consistent and memorable brand identity can help build brand awareness and customer loyalty over time.

5. Special products. Offering specialized products and services can meet unique customer needs and build loyalty. This may involve working with customers to develop custom products that meet their specific needs and preferences.

6. Analysis. The use of analytics is extremely important to develop effective marketing management techniques. Businesses can use data analytics to track marketing performance, make data-driven decisions, and continuously improve their marketing strategies. This includes tracking website traffic, social media engagement and other metrics to measure the effectiveness of marketing campaigns.

Developing effective marketing management techniques is critical to the success of any business and is especially important in the highly competitive yarn and textile industry. By implementing methods such as market research, digital marketing, participation in industry events, creating a strong brand identity, developing special products and using analytics, "Daka-Tex" LLC will have an advantage that distinguishes it from its competitors, expand its target audience, and strengthen its relationship with them. can communicate and, as a result, increase sales and increase revenues.

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